

INNOVATIVE TEACHING LEARNING METHODS

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Abstract

The education sector is changing and making an over haul change in the way it is disseminated to the present generation. Technology has crept into every aspect of teaching–learning process and tried to eradicate rote learning. With the advent of technology students are actively engaging in learning, and education has become more customized to the students. Teachers are becoming more of a facilitator and finding more time towards research as most of the repetitive tasks are done using technology As educators the primary focus is to ensure that students experience positive learning outcomes. Research, however, has shown that there are differences in students’ learning styles and that these differences will have an impact on the overall learning process. One way of ensuring that these positive outcomes are achieved is by identifying the different learning styles. Learning Style Inventory and provides various teaching methods to address the different students’ learning styles in order to enhance the learning process. Each of the Innovative methods of teaching to the students is examined based on the Learning styles adopted by students.

Keywords: Learning style, Innovative Teaching Methods, Technology, Creative Environment

1.Introduction

As we enter the third millennium, education via the internet, intranet or network represents great and exciting opportunities for both educators and learners. Educators have witnessed the rapid development of computer networks and improvement in the processing power of personal computers. In addition, the internet and World Wide Web (WWW) have made the computer a dynamic force in distance education, providing a new and interactive means of overcoming time and distance to reach learners (Wagschal, 1998)[1]. Electronic learning (e-learning) is an evolving, dynamic and rapidly changing educational opportunity that is a product of the advanced information technology environment. E-learning is essentially the network-enabled transfer of skills and knowledge (Anon, 2006)[2]. The internet is the largest, most powerful computer network in the world. It encompasses several million computers with internet addresses that are used by millions of people around the world. As increasingly more colleges, universities, elementary and secondary schools, companies and private citizens connect to the internet, more possibilities are opened for distance educators to overcome time and distance to reach students.[3] Through the internet, all sources of information on different subjects are available anytime, anywhere.

2.Objectives

1. To identify the learning styles by students
2. To identify some Innovative methods of teaching methods to enhance learning

3.Learning Styles

Several classifications of learning style and related concepts have been developed through the years. These classifications include Solomon's Inventory of Learning Styles, the Meyers-Briggs Type Indicator, Howard Gardner's multiple intelligences, McCarthy's 4-Mat system, and Honey and Mumford's (1986) social approach to learning. Perhaps the most widely known approach to assessing learning style, however, is that of David Kolb (1984).[4]

According to Kolb (1984) individuals learn in four stages or modes: concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. However, in different learning situations individuals often use different combinations of learning modes; hence no one mode clearly identifies an individual's learning style. The combination of learning modes forms four quadrants reflecting four learning styles: Accommodator, Diverger, Assimilator, and Converger.[5][6]

As indicated above, there is a need to accommodate different learning styles and modes. This accommodation requires more than recognizing the students' learning styles, however. Not only does learning style and mode vary by individual, but teaching style varies as well. Ebeling (2000) suggests that there is evidence most instructors use a teaching style that is comfortable to them and this is often the way they themselves learn best. According to Taylor (1998) all instructors need to be able to address a variety of learning styles and Kay (1998) proposes communication is improved by understanding how people learn. There is research to support varying teaching style to match learning style. Roach et al. (1993) examined alternative teaching styles in marketing classes. Filbeck and Smith (1996) looked at both teaching and learning styles along with age and gender. Borg and Shapiro (1996) studied teaching styles in economics classes. Hayes and Allinson (1996) analyzed 19 studies, which examined matching learning style to learning method and found support in 12 for improved learning performance. Dunn et al. (1995) discuss research showing higher grade point averages resulting from closer matches between teaching and learning styles.[7][8] Finally, Tomlinson (1996) emphasizes the need for instructors to be aware of and adapt to student learning styles.

It is also important to recognize that teaching style often determines course delivery methods. According to Mumford (1995) many activities fail to achieve their potential because they concentrate only on one stage of the learning cycle.[9][10] For example, lectures or books focus on delivering information while ignoring time to act practically on the information. Thus, we see that course delivery methods may impact course effectiveness as well as the differences in student learning styles.[11]

- Concrete experience (feeling): Learning from specific experiences and relating to people. Sensitive to other's feelings[12].

- Reflective observation (watching): Observing before making a judgment by viewing the environment from different perspectives. Looks for the meaning of things.[13]
- Abstract conceptualization (thinking): Logical analysis of ideas and acting on intellectual understanding of a situation.[14]
- Active experimentation (doing): Ability to get things done by influencing people and events through action. Includes risk-taking.[15]

Depending upon the situation or environment, the learners may enter the learning cycle at any point and will best learn the new task if they practice all four modes.

Learning Style	Description
Diverging (concrete, reflective)	Emphasizes the innovative and imaginative approach to doing things. Views concrete situations from many perspectives and adapts by observation rather than by action. Interested in people and tends to be feeling-oriented. Likes such activities as cooperative groups and brainstorming.
Assimilating (abstract, reflective)	Pulls a number of different observations and thoughts into an integrated whole. Likes to reason inductively and create models and theories. Likes to design projects and experiments.
Converging (abstract, active)	Emphasizes the practical application of ideas and solving problems. Likes decision-making, problem-solving, and the practical application of ideas. Prefers technical problems over interpersonal issues.
Accommodating (concrete, active)	Uses trial and error rather than thought and reflection. Good at adapting to changing circumstances; solves problems in an intuitive, trial-and-error manner, such as discovery learning. Also tends to be at ease with people.

4. Innovative methods to accommodate various styles

Educators may not be able to accommodate the learning styles of each student; however, they can design their courses and use a variety of teaching methods to ensure that learners benefit from a comfortable and rewarding experience. Many researchers have suggested that students should be encouraged to use all four learning styles instead of relying on one style. In addition to the usual lecture method, several other pedagogical vehicles can be considered to address the different learning styles.

Computer-based simulation exercises - Simulation exercises are available for several disciplines and have been used quite extensively as a tool to enhance the learning process. In essence, users learn by simulation. Exercises or games are developed to simulate real situations or scenarios and require users to use various skills, and knowledge and often require them to take risks and to experiment with things. The power of simulations is that they engage students more and students are more likely to learn from them as compared to the standard lecture (Andrade, 2007). Simulation, therefore, would be a desirable tool to use to stimulate the interest of accommodators. According to Kolb (1984) accommodators learn primarily from hands-on experience and intuition rather than from logical analysis.[16][17]

Projects/summer internship – projects are widely used where individuals are encouraged to work either on a topic chosen by the instructor or one chosen by students where they are expected to generate a wide range of ideas and gather information. This process requires them to become creative and view situations from different perspectives. This vehicle would enhance the learning process of divergers

Case Analysis – This is another popular tool used to develop analytical thinking. Students are required to use the information presented and to be able to put information into concise and logical form, which is consistent with case studies. Strength of assimilators is their propensity to define problems and this is quite relevant to the case study method.

Z to A approach is experiential learning. Experiential learning is inductive, learner centered, and activity oriented. Personalized reflection about an experience and the formulation of plans to apply learning to other contexts are critical factors in effective experiential learning. The emphasis in experiential learning is on the process of learning and not on the product. Experiential learning can be viewed as a cycle consisting of five phases, all of which are necessary:

- Experiencing (an activity occurs);
- Sharing or publishing (reactions and observations are shared);
- Analyzing or processing (patterns and dynamics are determined);
- Inferring or generalizing (principles are derived); and,
- Applying (plans are made to use learning in new situations).

5. Conclusion

From the above discussion it is seen that there are different learning styles that can be best suited to get oneself involved in the teaching learning process. Accordingly a number of innovative methods can be adopted to enhance the learning process. It is necessary to understand the audience and choose the best suited method of teaching so that the learning environment is creative and both the parties benefit from this.

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